

ORGANIZATION OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING USING PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES

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ABSTRACT

Information is presented on the influence of a student-oriented approach on the creation of a favorable educational environment. The main emphasis is on interactive technologies for teaching schoolchildren. The forms of working with electronic resources are described, and there is information about educational portals for school students and parents. The article will be of interest to workers in the education sector.

INTRODUCTION

The modern world is dynamically developing and changing. A successful professional and social career these days is impossible without the willingness to master new technologies, adapt to different working conditions, solve new professional problems, and bring creative ideas to life.

It is no longer effective to conduct a traditional lesson, since it will not cause a sufficient response from students, and, accordingly, will not contribute to increasing learning motivation. Therefore, the teacher is forced to use various methods in foreign language lessons that could contribute to the development of the child and give him the opportunity to be a competitive person integrated into interethnic communications.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Of course, every teacher chooses the technologies that are optimal for their work. But there are also universal ones that allow you to build a high-quality educational process. The person-centered approach is at the forefront, since it is this that contributes to the creation of a learning and educational environment favorable for the student.

The need to place the student at the center of the educational process, to make him an active subject of learning activities, to organize his interaction with other students, to give the educational process a real practical orientation - this is the only way in the realities of the modern world to maintain the motivation of students to study such a complex subject as a foreign language.

Project technology, critical thinking technology and interactive technologies allow you to reveal the personal potential of each child in English lessons [1].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The latter allow you to organize multilateral communication in foreign language lessons, when a dialogue arises between all participants in the lesson. The student becomes liberated and gains self-confidence, which cannot but contribute to his activity in studying the subject and the practical use of the language.

The essence of interactive learning lies in a certain organization of the educational process. Almost all students involved in the process of learning have the opportunity to understand and reflect on what they know and think.

Interactive technologies involve [2]:

- dialogue communication;
- acquisition of independently acquired experienced knowledge and skills;
- development of critical thinking;
- development of problem solving skills;
- formation of personal qualities of students.

Interactive learning simultaneously solves several problems: develops communication skills, helps establish emotional contacts between participants in the learning process, solves an information problem, since it provides students with the necessary information, without which it is impossible to carry out joint activities; develops general educational skills and provides an educational task, as it teaches students to work in a team.

Here are some of the working methods:

1. Gaming technologies. They are most relevant for lessons in primary school, as they allow them to learn the material in a form familiar to children. However, we should not forget about games with older students. The children also enjoy participating in play activities [3].
2. "FISHBONE" technique. (Fish skeleton). Its essence lies in analyzing the problem "in its bones." The head of the fish is the problem itself, the bones are the causes of the problem and how to solve them, the tail is the conclusion.
3. Cluster reception. A cluster (English cluster - cluster, brush, swarm) is a union of several homogeneous elements, which can be considered as an independent unit with certain properties. This is a graphical form of organizing information when the main semantic units are identified and recorded in the form of a diagram indicating all the connections between them. It is an image that helps to systematize and generalize educational material. The cluster method develops systemic thinking, teaches students to systematize not only educational material, but also their value judgments, express their opinions, which are formed on the basis of observations, experience and new knowledge gained, develops the skills of simultaneous consideration of several positions, and the ability to creatively process information.

There are a huge number of methods that allow you to use interactive learning. The teacher can independently come up with new forms of working with the class. However, it is worth emphasizing that the effectiveness of the techniques varies in each class.

Students may differ in their level of preparedness, educational motivation, and emotional characteristics. Therefore, the teacher needs to select the most effective and optimal forms and methods of work in order to achieve the goals and intended results. It is also necessary to take into account the age characteristics of students, to adequately assess

the goals and objectives that the teacher sets for the lesson in order to achieve the desired result.

Internet resources provide enormous assistance in the use of interactive technologies in foreign language lessons. They can be used for:

- inclusion in the lesson content, that is, to integrate them into the curriculum;
- independent, in-depth study, eliminating gaps in knowledge, skills, abilities;
- students' search for information while working on a project (individual or group);
- independent preparation for passing the qualifying exam as an external student;
- systematic study of a specific foreign language course remotely under the guidance of a teacher.

A teacher can use the information resources of the global network and the services provided by it in different ways in the educational process in the classroom.

Firstly, it is possible to use specially designed training programs on the Internet, which provide materials for different types of speech activity, different aspects of language; A methodology for using them in the classroom is also proposed. Various educational portals for children (Uchi.ru, cambridgeenglish.org, EnglishforKids, etc.) do an excellent job of this task.

Secondly, it is possible to carry out an independent selection of individual materials, which can be adapted, at the discretion of the teacher, to the specific educational tasks of a certain group of students. This category of resources offers a wider field for teacher creativity: thematic presentations, videos, music files and much more.

The main goal of using the Internet is the formation of communicative competence within the framework of a person-oriented approach, which involves the formation of the ability for intercultural interaction. Computer telecommunications provide this opportunity. The student enters into a live dialogue (written or oral) with a real native speaker partner.

CONCLUSION

Of course, you shouldn't completely abandon time-tested methods of work in pursuit of novelty and interactivity. The ideal option is to include innovation in the context of a traditional lesson. As you know, "everything new is well forgotten old."

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